

Modelling surface and underground streams in drainage network computation

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Context

- **DTM alteration** from drainage network calculation using the **D8 method**.
- **Invisibility of culverts**, crucial underground features on the DTM.
- No **semantic modelling** of watercourses.

DEM and culverts - Data source: MRNF and ULaval

Aim

- Developing a **conceptual model** describing drainage network including underground flows.
- Adding **semantic** knowledge to watercourses.

Conceptual Model

- Including terrain features for watershed and depression management : comprehensive management of hydrological processes.

Results

connecting culverts to thalwegs

3D view with elevation profile (a), top view of delimited culverts (b)

Network of thalwegs and ridges

Flow direction

Watercourses and watersheds

Additional data analysis tool

Conclusion

- Creation of a **complete topological structure** for the network.
- Correct calculation of **surface and underground flows without altering the DTM**.